

A DNA-NDI hybrid to efficiently detect histone in parts per trillion (ppt) level

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Abstract

Amine and acid functionalized naphthalenediimide (NDI) derivatives were designed and synthesized. The binding affinity of these derivatives were analysed in presence of DNA to identify the most suitable NDI derivative that can be utilized for the detection of histone, a DNA-binding protein. In the monomeric state, the NDI derivatives show high fluorescence but in presence of DNA, the emission quenched. The “turn-off” of emission can be attributed to the formation of NDI-DNA nano-hybrid. Histone, having a stronger binding

affinity toward DNA, displaces NDI from DNA. The displacement of NDI leads to fluorescence back to the original monomeric state. So, the quenching

of the fluorescence of NDI upon binding with DNA is used to quantitative “turn on” detection of histone with extremely high efficiency and selectivity.

DNA, Histone, Intercalation, Naphthalenediimide, Sensor

References

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